

Translator's Note: The original research document, **co-authored** by **Davit Oboladze** and produced in Georgian, consists of 73 pages. For international assessment purposes, the English translation includes the author-attributed title page, table of contents, and introductory analytical sections (first three pages), as specified by the commissioning party.

The complete Georgian-language report remains available in full and is referenced accordingly.

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Service Delivery Policy and Strategy in Georgia's National Food Agency

An Institutional Assessment

Tbilisi, Georgia

This research report was prepared by the **Innovations and Reforms Center (IRC)** with the support of the **United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)** and the **Government of the United Kingdom through UK aid**. The views and conclusions expressed herein are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official policies or positions of the supporting organisations.

This research was conducted by the **research team** of the Innovations and Reforms Center (IRC) and was co-authored by **Mariam Nafetvaridze** and **Davit Oboladze**.

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Introduction

On 12 April 2022, the Government of Georgia approved the Public Service Development Strategy, marking a systemic shift in how public service-provider state institutions are expected to approach service design, development, and management. From this point onward, public authorities were required to move beyond ad hoc service provision and institutionalise the methodologies, principles, and tools articulated in the Strategy. The implementation of these methodologies across public institutions is critical for establishing a coherent, standardised, and governance-oriented framework for public service management nationwide.

To support the practical operationalisation of the Strategy, the Innovations and Reforms Center (IRC), with the support of the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), launched the project '*Supporting the Implementation of the Public Service Development Strategy*' in 2022. The project aims to strengthen the capacity of public institutions in public service management through structured knowledge transfer and the application of external analytical expertise to service redesign processes. The National Food Agency of Georgia (hereafter, the Agency) was selected as one of the pilot institutions for the introduction and application of service design methodology.

Within the framework of the UNDP-supported initiative, IRC developed a service design policy guideline tailored to the Agency's policy mandate, institutional structure, and operational capacity. The guideline serves as a practical policy instrument to support public officials in the systematic creation, redesign, and improvement of public services, embedding user-centred and evidence-informed principles into routine administrative practice.

To operationalise the guideline, IRC applied its methodology to a selected Agency service through an applied policy evaluation process. By agreement with the Agency, the Food and Food-Related Packaging Hygiene Certification Service (hereinafter referred to as the Hygiene Certificate) was selected for redesign. The redesign process adopted a learning-by-doing approach, ensuring the direct involvement of Agency staff throughout all stages of analysis and design. This approach generated service-specific solutions while simultaneously strengthening institutional capacity by enhancing staff understanding of service design processes and analytical tools.

This research report presents the activities undertaken and findings identified during the *discovery phase*, as well as the analytical work conducted during the *opportunity phase*, including the formulation of concrete, evidence-based solutions aimed at improving service performance, accessibility, and institutional coherence.